

Amboni Caves

By Maximilian Chami, University of Dar es Salaam

Entry tags: Limestone karst, Coastal NEC Bantu, Religious Group, Abrahamic, African Religions, Bantoid, Islam, Cave or Cavern, Sabaki-Swahili, Atlantic-Congo, Benue-Congo, Northeast Coastal Bantu, Swahili, Volta-Congo, Mombasa-Lamu-Inland Swahili, Northeast Savanna Bantu, East Bantu, Southern Bantoid, Christian, Language, Narrow Bantu, Swahili (G.40), Religious Place, African Religion, Islam

Ritual practices.

Date Range: 40000 BCE - 2024 CE

Region: Amboni Caves, Tanga Region

Region tags: Tanga, Tanzania, Africa, Eastern Africa

Limestone Caves

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Amboni Caves, Chami, Maximilian F.. "Management of Sacred Heritage Places in Tanzania: A Case of Kuumbi Limestone Cave, Zanzibar Island". *Journal of Heritage Management* 5, no. 1 (June 2020): 71-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2455929620934342>.

Reference: Amboni Caves, Chami, Maximilian. "Community Involvement and Sustainable Tourism Development in Heritage Management: Amboni Limestone Caves, Tanzania". *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism, and Leisure* 7, no. 2 (n.d.): 1-13.

Reference: Amboni Caves, Peter, Mandela . *Archaeological Study of Amboni Limestone Cave, Tanga in Northeastern Coast of Tanzania*. Dar Es Salaam. Dar es Salaam: University of Dar es Salaam, 2013.

Reference: Amboni Caves, Peter, Mandela. "An Archaeological Study of Amboni Limestone Caves, Tanga Region in the Northern Coast of Tanzania". *Studies in the African Past* 12 (n.d.): 128-43.

Reference: Amboni Caves, Matthews, P. "Site Description and Conservation Evaluation: Amboni Caves and Mkulumuzi River Valley, Tanga Municipality, Tanzania. London, U.K: The Society for Environmental Exploration and the University of Dar Es Salaam, London.", 1995.